

Impact of Feature Scaling on the Performance of Classification Algorithms:

a Comparative Study on Wine Dataset

(Suhani Arora)

Abstract-

This study shows the impact of feature scaling on the performance of classification algorithms using the Wine dataset. Five classifiers were evaluated with and without applying standardization- Logistic Regression, KNN, SVM, Decision Tree, and Random Forest.

The results show that distance-based classifiers show huge improvement in performance after feature scaling, but the tree-based models remain largely unaffected. The findings show that the effect of feature scaling depends on what classification algorithm is used.

Introduction-

Classification is a Machine Learning Technique that aims to assign data in the correct label. These labels are called classes. The algorithms learn the characteristics of classes, then use it to classify the new unseen data. The characteristics of classes can be referred to as features. [3]

When the features are numerical attributes with very different scales (Example- one feature ranges from 1 to 10, while the other feature ranges from 30-60), most algorithms do not perform well. In this situation, a transformation is performed called feature scaling. Commonly used feature scaling methods are- (1) Min-Max scaling: Here values are rescaled to be in a range usually between 0 to 1. This is commonly used for algorithms like Neural Networks. (2) Standardization scaling: Here data is rescaled such that mean=0 and standard deviation=1. It is commonly used in distance-based algorithms like KNN, SVM, Logistic Regression. On the other hand, tree-based algorithms, like Decision Trees and Random Forest, are not impacted by scaling

because they use threshold-based comparisons and feature splitting to form output, not distance, gradient or magnitude. [2]

This study aims to analyse the impact of feature scaling on different classification algorithms on wine dataset.

Dataset Description-

The “Wine dataset” was used to analyse the impact of feature scaling. The dataset contained 178 samples, each representing the chemical analysis of a wine. Each sample has 13 numerical features, namely alcohol, malic acid, ash, alcalinity of ash, magnesium, total phenols, flavanoids, nonflavanoid phenols, proanthocyanins, color intensity, hue, OD280/OD315 of diluted wines and proline.

The database has 3 different classes, corresponding to different wines. All features are numerical, making it suitable for applying statistical and distance-based classification techniques.

Another notable characteristic of the Wine dataset is the variation in feature ranges. Example-features like Hue are very small in value, while features like Proline are very large. [1]

Methodology-

This section explains how the dataset was pre-processed, which classification algorithms were used, and how their performance was evaluated.

A. Data Pre-processing

The dataset was first divided into training and testing data using an 80:20 split, where 80% of the data was used to train and the 20% was used to test. ‘Stratified split’ was used to make sure that all three classes were equally trained upon and tested upon.

‘StandardScaler’ was used for feature scaling. To avoid data leakage, the scaler was fitted only on the training data, and then the same scaling parameters were applied to the testing

data. The experiments were done in two settings: once without feature scaling, and once with feature scaling.

B. Classification Algorithms

Five commonly used classification algorithms were used, that are:

- Logistic Regression
- K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)
- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- Decision Tree
- Random Forest

These algorithms were chosen to represent different learning methods, including both distance-based and tree-based methods.

C. Evaluation Metrics

The performance of each classifier was evaluated using standard metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1-score.

Experimental Setup-

Two experiments were done to evaluate the impact of feature scaling on classification algorithms. In the first experiment, all classification algorithms were trained and tested using the original unscaled features. In the second experiment, the same was done after applying feature scaling using StandardScaler.

To ensure a fair comparison, the same train-test split, random state, and model parameters were used across both experiments. All experiments were implemented using Python with the scikit-learn library and were executed on Google Colab.

Results-

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Logistic Regression	0.972222	0.977778	0.966667	0.970962
KNN	0.805556	0.801865	0.804762	0.802469
SVM	0.694444	0.508454	0.638889	0.557808
Decision Tree	0.944444	0.958333	0.938889	0.945741
Random Forest	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000

Table 1: Without Scaling

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Logistic Regression	0.972222	0.977778	0.966667	0.970962
KNN	0.972222	0.969697	0.976190	0.971781
SVM	0.972222	0.977778	0.966667	0.970962
Decision Tree	0.944444	0.958333	0.938889	0.945741
Random Forest	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000

Table 2: With Scaling

The classification performance of the algorithms without feature scaling is presented in Table 1, and the performance after standardization is presented in Table 2.

While the performance of Logistic Regression, Decision Tree and Random Forest remain unaffected by scaling, distance-based algorithms KNN and SVM show noticeable performance differences.

Discussion-

The result showed that feature scaling has a huge impact on certain classification algorithms, particularly those that rely on distance calculation. KNN (K-Nearest Neighbours) and SVM

(Support Vector Machine) showed substantial improvement after standardization, highlighting the importance of equal feature contribution during model training.

Logistic Regression showed stable accuracy in both scaled and unscaled scenarios.

Tree-based classifiers, including Decision Tree and Random Forest, were not at all affected by feature scaling. This is expected as these models rely on feature splitting on the basis of threshold, rather than distance or magnitude.

This shows that pre-processing techniques should be based on the algorithm and its characteristics and should not be applied uniformly.

Conclusion-

The study shows the impact of feature scaling on the performance of different classification algorithms using the Wine Dataset. Two experiments were performed- once with, and second without feature scaling using Standardization. The results indicate that feature scaling significantly improves the performance of distance-based classifiers, while having minimal effect on tree-based models.

The findings confirm that the influence of feature scaling is algorithm-dependent, and proper pre-processing plays a crucial role in improving model performance and stability.

Resources-

[1] : Tawfik Elmetwally, and Kaggle. *Wine dataset*. Wine recognition for data exploration and Classification. 2024. *Wine dataset.csv*,

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/tawfikelmetwally/wine-dataset>.

[2] : Aurélien Géron. “*Hands-On Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn and TensorFlow*”.

O’Reilly Media, 2017. *Academia.edu*,

https://www.academia.edu/43840124/Hands_On_Machine_Learning_with_Scikit_Learn_

Keras_and_TensorFlow_SECOND_EDITION_Concepts_Tools_and_Techniques_to_Build_Intelligent_Systems.

- [3] : IBM, and Ivan Belcic. “What is Classification in Machine Learning?” *IBM*, <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/classification-machine-learning>. Accessed 1 January 2026.